

Analysis of Seam Strength in the Development of Women's Clothing from National Fabric

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Abstract: *The article examines the problem of the expansion of warp threads in the seams of clothing parts during developing women's clothing from the national adras fabric. Researches were conducted on a new elastic structure sample of the national fabric.*

Keywords: *National fabric, Women's clothing, Seam strength, Material analysis, Textile design, Sewing technology, Mechanical properties of fabric, Seam testing.*

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The demand for natural products, in particular, textile and light industry products made from natural cotton and silk fibers, is growing day by day in the world market. In this regard, it is urgent and important to continuously improve the quality and competitiveness of modern sewing products, expand their assortment. Currently, great importance is attached to the use of new technologies to improve the quality of sewing products. In this regard, strengthening competitiveness in this industry requires investment in scientific developments and the introduction of production, which is a necessary measure to ensure the resistance of manufacturers to strong competitive pressure.

In the world, scientific research is being conducted to develop innovative techniques and technologies for the textile and light industry, which provide for the effective use of modern scientific and technical achievements, and to improve existing ones. In this regard, more and more attention is paid to the development of scientific foundations of the technology of manufacturing garments, determining the optimal parameters affecting the product in the technological process, expanding the range of competitive products, developing scientific developments for the effective use of local raw materials, ensuring the strength of thread connections of garments and reducing raw material consumption, and introducing resource-saving innovative technologies into production.

The demand for our national fabrics is increasing day by day and there is great interest not only in our republic, but also in foreign countries. Adras is a type of fabric with a warp made of natural silk and a thick warp made of thick yarn. One side of the adras is smooth like satin, and the other side is shiny. The flowers are made in the abr method, and yellow, blue, pink, red colors are used. A number of research works have been carried out to create new types and patterns of abrband fabrics, improve consumer properties, and create new types of assortment [1]. This scientific research work is devoted to a new assortment of satin and adras fabrics with stretch properties, and technological indicators of samples of national textile products with new compositional stretch properties were analyzed.

One of the main indicators of the operational properties of seams in sewing products is the slippage of fabric threads during the seam. A study of thread slippage in materials shows that it occurs in adras fabrics, in fabrics with a low density for shirts and suits. Slippage of fabric threads occurs in those areas that are most exposed to stress during stretching: the middle seam of the back, waist seams, side seams, and the seam where the sleeve is attached to the shoulder. The high strength of the fabric and seams does not guarantee the reliability of the product, since damage may occur during the seam.

Fabric shear studies have shown that in most fabrics, shear occurs in the warp direction. Shear along the warp direction is observed in suiting fabrics. It was found that shear is characteristic of adras, house satin, suiting jacquard, shirt satin and lining viscose fabrics. The study of the structure of fabrics showed that the lower the surface density, the higher the shear [2].

The influence of various factors on the shear of fabric threads in the seam was studied. Studies of the shear indicators of threads during the seam were carried out on samples of the existing adras fabric consisting of 100% cotton fiber in the warp and weft and a newly developed adras fabric with 100% cotton fiber in the warp and 70% cotton fiber in the warp and 30% elastane fiber added.

Determination of shear and strength along the seam

Table 1.

№	Fabric fiber composition	Breaking strength, N		Elongation at break, mm		Thread slippage in the seam, mm		Surface density, d/m ²
		Tanda	Arqoq	Tanda	Arqoq	Tanda	Arqoq	
1	Available fabric Cotton+cotton (100%)	92	288	46	31	2	2.5	156,4
2	Stretchy mesh fabric Cotton (70%) + elastane (30%)	126	201	35	103	0.28	0.08	180,8

The results of the study of the effect of the length of the skein on the slippage of the threads in the seam showed that increasing the length of the skein in the skein increases the magnitude of the slippage during the seam. That is, if the number of skeins in 1 cm increases, the slippage in the seam decreases. Therefore, in fabrics with high slippage, it is necessary to increase the stitch frequency in 1 cm. Reducing the skein length increases the friction force between the fabric threads and reduces their tendency to slip. For samples taken from the Adras fabric, the skein length is considered to be 1.5-2 cm (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dependence of thread displacement in a seam on the length of the seam

Studies of the structure of fabrics have shown that the lower the surface density, the higher the slip. As the density of fabrics increases, the more the threads bend, making it more difficult for them to slide in the warp or weft direction. Therefore, the higher the fabric density in one direction, the less the slip, for example, the less the slip along the warp compared to the weft, the more along the weft, and vice versa. The slip of fabric threads along the seam leads to the formation of gaps between the warp threads of the fabric parallel to the seam threads, which reduces the strength of the seam and worsens the appearance of the product. In the garment industry, this defect is expected to occur, but it is impossible to completely prevent it, only attempts have been made to reduce the magnitude of the slip. In order to prevent slip, the need arose to introduce additional operations in the garment industry to improve the structure of the material and ensure seam strength. Improving the strength characteristics of thread joints in sparsely woven fabrics allows you to increase the quality of garments and extend their service life.

When studying the nature of the shear anisotropy of threads during sewing, it was found that plastic deformation of the samples occurs simultaneously with the shear of the threads in the seam, and an inverse relationship between shear and plastic deformation was observed. The choice of a rational design solution depending on the direction of the seams affects the quality of thread joints in clothing [3]. The calculation of the relationship between the shear of threads and the plastic deformation of the fabric allows you to choose the size of the seam allowance in clothing based on the size of the seam allowance. If the number of stitches per 1 cm increases, the shear in the seam decreases. Reducing the length of the stitch increases the friction force between the fabric threads and reduces their shear properties. For fabrics with high shear, it is necessary to correctly select the mode of thread joints. In the manufacture of sewing products, seams of various designs are used, these are binding, sewing and decorative seams. The main load falls mainly on the binding seams, with which the side, shoulder, middle and relief cuts of the product are sewn. The greatest displacement was observed in unprocessed split-ironed and laid-ironed binding seams. In overcast seams, displacement occurs on the side of the unprocessed seam allowance. In traditional technology, the seam allowance is often reinforced with an additional adhesive tape, but this, in turn, leads to excessive thickening [4,5].

The results of the study show that the thread displacement in the seams of the samples depends on the seam design. The greatest resistance to displacement was observed in the seam allowance, which was reinforced with an additional stabilizer at a distance of 2 mm. The greatest slippage was observed in poorly ironed and laid-ironed seams. However, in the development of outerwear, mainly ironed and laid-ironed seams are used. It was in these seams that the greatest slippage of threads was observed.

The obtained data allow us to scientifically substantiate recommendations for improving the quality of thread connections depending on the direction of the seams and to choose a rational design when designing clothes from sparsely woven fabrics.

References:

1. N.B. Yusupova, Sh.R. Umarova, E.Sh. Alimbayev. Decoration of fabrics by changing the composition of the thread // Scientific and technical journal "Textile problems" TTYSI 2021, issue 4 (05.00.00: №17)
2. Alimukhamedova B.G., Akhmedov M.A. Study of the expandability of threads in the seams of knitted materials // Collection of scientific articles of the international scientific and practical conference "Innovation and modern technologies in the fashion industry" held within the framework of the Tashkent Fashion Week, TTESI, November 23, 2019, p. 47-50

3. Alimukhamedova B.G. Development of methods for ensuring the strength properties of thread connections of sewing products. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences. Tashkent–2021.
4. Barno Alimukhamedova, Munira Babadzhanova. Technology of treatment of seams with polymer composition to eliminate spreading. *Journal of Hunan University (Natural Sciences)* vol. 49. No. 12. December 2022, p.1621-1626.
5. Mastura Rasulova, Shohista Mamasolieva, Munira Babadjanova, et al. Selection of sewing thread for connecting details of workwear from fabrics of new structures. Cite as: *AIP Conference Proceedings* 2430, 030007 (2022); <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0076965>. Published Online: 24 January 2022.